

Agroforestry and Pillar I

- Pillar I CAP is associated with direct payments for farmers once both social and environmental conditionality are fulfilled.
- Pillar I fosters sustainable land management in different agricultural land uses (croplands, permanent grasslands and permanent crops) on a voluntary basis to **combat climate change** through mitigation and adaptation interventions, **protect habitats** considering water, soil and biodiversity and reducing pesticides use and **enhance health** by promoting animal welfare

Agroforestry ecoscheme

Agroforestry practices are recognized as such by the ecoschemes, mainly linked to the two main practices of agroforestry: silvopasture (if they are highly biodiverse) and agrosilvicultural practices linked to the establishment, maintenance and cutting plan of agroforestry systems. However, agroforestry can be part as a practice of the CAP proposed list of ecoschemes linked to different types of sustainable farming and livestock systems. Figure 1 shows the agroforestry ecoscheme interventions linked to the use of landscape features, the promotion of grass cover on permanent crops that can be grazed, the production of berries in forest lands and agroforestry as such linked to silvopasture in Greece and to agrosilviculture in Germany. Countries such as Spain, among others, did not promote agroforestry ecoschemes as they are linked to the Pillar II as seen in the Policy Brief number 11.

FIGURE 1. Agroforestry ecoscheme interventions

Agroforestry and farming systems

Agroforestry as a way to sustainability managing the land is a tool extensively used in organic, integrated pest management, carbon farming, high nature value and precision farming systems as it contributes to promote the incorporation of organic matter therefore mitigating climate change (i.e. atmospheric CO₂ intake and Soil Organic matter incorporation) and reducing soil pollution, reduce pest and diseases by increasing the presence of natural enemies, enhance the nutrient recycling by capturing and up-taking released top-layer nutrients and incorporating those nutrients to topsoil before leaching to groundwaters is produced protecting water and soils and finally protecting high nature value areas as agroforestry optimize the use of the resources in marginal lands linked to the prevention of soil and wind erosion. However, agroforestry is not directly mentioned in the explanation of these eco-schemes by the CAP.

FIGURE 2. Goats grazing shrublands in Ancares (Spain). Source: Couso-Viana. A.

Agroforestry and livestock ecoschemes

Agroforestry is linked to livestock as both the high and below layers are able to be used as feeding,

provides more space enhancing animal welfare that promotes robustness, fertility, longevity and adaptability. Moreover, agroforestry has been recognized as an excellent way to reduce gut nematodes (i.e. goats consumption of woody perennials)

MAIN CONCLUSIONS

- Agroforestry is part of the list of CAP 2023-2027 ecoschemes
- Most of the agroforestry ecoschemes are linked to silvopasture, but also landscape features are promoted.
- Most of the list of ecoschemes can be linked to agroforestry at some extent (i.e. farming systems and livestock), but agroforestry itself is not clearly recognized.

María Rosa Mosquera Losada, Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro, José Javier Santiago Freijanes, Nuria Ferreiro Domínguez & Ana Couso Viana (2025) Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

References

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